

DEVELOPMENT OF A CONTINUOUS RAMIE SINGLE YARN REINFORCED COMPOSITE STRAND

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1 Introduction

Glass fibers, one of the representative reinforcements for polymer matrix composites, have many excellent physical and mechanical properties such as low density, heat resistance, wear resistance, high specific strength and stiffness and so on. Glass fiber reinforced composites have thus been investigated for many years because of their huge demands in industry. On the other hand, they have disadvantage such as difficulty in disposing at their final lifetime. Global environmental problems and energy shortage have brought the focus of making alternative materials from biomass resources all over the world. Natural fibers have become suitable alternatives to glass fibers. They are abundant, biodegradable, renewable, and have similar specific properties to glass fibers [1]. Thus, there has been increasing attention to improvement of natural fibers as reinforcement of polymer matrix composites that can be replaced for petroleum-based fibers dominated in various fields so far.

Ramie fibers that have advantages of high tenacity, silk-like luster, and resistance to bacteria are one of well-known natural fibers to be used as a textile fiber [2]. Short ramie fibers-polypropylene (PP) composites have been studied by another's group [3]. The main problem occurring in the reference [3] was low mechanical properties caused by short fiber length distribution, because natural

fibers were inserted directly into extrusion machine.

It has been reported by Tanaka and Hirano [4] to produce long natural fiber reinforced thermoplastic. It gives composites with much higher mechanical properties in comparison with short fiber reinforced composites due to the effects of longer fiber length. On the other hand, the disadvantage is that fabrication procedures are complicated.

In this study, thus, the continuous ramie single yarn reinforced polypropylene (PP) composite strands were developed using a new and relatively simple technique. The strands were pelletized and injection-moulded, and their tensile properties were investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Continuous ramie single yarns, having a fineness of 95 tex, Type No. 16 (TOSCO, Co., Japan) and polypropylene (Prime Polymer Co., Ltd.) were used as reinforcements and matrix material, respectively. Physical and chemical properties of ramie fibers are listed in Table 1 [5]. Maleric anhydride modified poly-propylene (MA-PP, Kayaku Akzo Co, Ltd.) was also used as a coupling agent to promote better fiber-matrix interaction in this study.

2.2 Fabrication procedures

Table 1 Physical and chemical properties of ramie fibers

Density (g/cm ³)	Microfibril angle (°)	Moisture content (wt%)	Chemical composition (wt%)			
			Cellulose	Lignin	Hemicellulose	Pectin Wax
1.50	7.5	8.0	68.6-76.2	0.6-0.7	13.1-16.7	1.9 0.3

Fig. 1 Schematic view of a combined technique

Continuous ramie single yarn/PP composites were produced by a new combined technique which consists of coating and resin impregnation processes as shown in Fig. 1. The continuous ramie single yarns were first delivered into a cross-head die attached to a ϕ 15mm single screw extruder (Spinning machine, Musashino Kikai Co, Ltd), into which PP pellets and MA-PP powders were fed at the same time. After the mixed resin was coated on the yarns in the die, it was impregnated into inter-fibers through multi-pin system. The number of pins used here was 22. Temperatures of the single screw extruder were all set at 190°C with a screw speed of 7.0 r.p.m. Set temperatures were 160-225 °C for resin impregnation process. A motor was set to draw the composite strand with a screw speed of 450 r.p.m. The continuous ramie strand was chopped into pellets of 2mm length. The pellets were moulded into small-sized and mid-sized tensile specimens on an injection moulding machine, as shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively. The temperatures were set at 180-185 °C for moulding. Fiber contents of small-sized and mid-sized specimens were 30wt% and 10-50wt%, respectively.

Fig. 2 Shape and dimension of small-sized tensile specimen

Fig. 3 Shape and dimension of mid-sized tensile specimen

2.3 Tensile test

Tensile tests were carried out using a universal testing machine (Ritorusensuta small desktop tester, JT Tosi Co, Ltd) for small-sized specimens, and tensile and compression testing machine (Minebea Co, Ltd) for mid-sized specimens at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min and 17 mm/min, respectively. The mean cross-section area of all specimens was measured on three locations along the longitudinal direction using a micrometer and then taking an average. Five specimens were tested for each condition to obtain an average value.

3 Results

3.1 Degree of continuous strand impregnation of a combine technique

There have been various attempts to produce complete composites from reinforcement using glass/natural fibers with thermoplastic matrices. The main problem is that fibers are needed to be longer than those critical lengths in order to increase mechanical properties of composites. One of possible methods is pultrusion technique used by ICI for the manufacture of Vertron long fiber moulding materials [6]. The impregnation devices applied in the past are simple in form used in the processing of thermosets [7]. One of the most important points is to achieve good impregnation.

The microscopic cross-section images of ramie/PP composite strands are shown in Fig. 4. It can be observed that not only resin is locally infiltrated, but relatively large amount of voids can be seen between fibers before resin impregnation process in Fig. 4 (a). Fig. 4 (b) and (c) show images after 11th pin and 15th pin, respectively. It has almost

Fig. 4 The cross-section images of ramie/PP composite strands: (a) before resin impregnation process, (b) after 11th pin, (c) after 15th pin and (d) final product. (The images in (a) and (d) are obtained by 3D laser measuring microscope and the images in (b) and (c) are obtained by scanning electron microscopy.)

no void. Final product in Fig. 4 (d) shows that any void does not occur. It is well verified that the attached multi-pin system obviously assists in impregnation the resin into inter-fibers by its contact pressure. In other words, the composite strands can be successfully be produced through such a combined technique, coating and resin impregnation processes.

3.2 Tensile properties

Fig. 5 shows typical tensile stress-strain curves of short ramie/PP reinforced composites containing 30 wt% fiber content using small-sized specimens. The result shows the dependency on different temperatures during resin impregnation process. That is to say, it can be seen that there is an optimal temperature giving higher strength and elastic

modulus. Table 1 shows the result of tensile properties of short ramie/PP reinforced composites. As in the table, it can be seen that tensile strength and Young's modulus increases with increasing temperature over the whole 160-195°C range. It was observed that relatively low temperature produced voids between fibers similar to Fig. 4 (a) even during resin impregnation process.

Eventually, composites specimens of 195°C not only tensile strength are improved 1.63 times higher than PP specimens, but Young's modulus is increased 1.87 times. These results well verify the impregnation of rein to any space between short ramie fibers by means of resin impregnation process.

On the other hand, there is a gradual decrease in tensile strength as the temperature increases. It

Fig. 5 Typical stress-strain curves of short ramie/PP reinforced composites at different temperatures during resin impregnation process

indicates that over-heating causes degradation of ramie fibers during resin impregnation process. The maximum properties of composites are thus obtained at 195°C, and above this temperature the tensile strength of composite specimens are decreased due to over-heat.

Fig. 6 shows the results of tensile strength using mid-sized specimens at different fiber content. It can be seen that tensile strength increases with increasing fiber content. This trend reaches a maximum level at 40 wt%. Tensile strength of 40 wt% increased 1.73 times higher than PP specimens.

Table 1 Tensile properties of short ramie/PP composite specimens

Material	T _{rip} °C	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Fracture strain (%)
PP (0wt%)	—	1.04 (7.12)	42.4 (2.70)	>200
Composite	160	1.45 (11.3)	50.6 (5.29)	5.65 (8.28)
	185	1.64 (8.03)	55.1 (6.58)	5.32 (7.65)
	195	1.94 (7.16)	69.2 (4.57)	5.37 (3.97)
	205	1.72 (11.8)	67.7 (3.20)	5.26 (3.88)
	225	1.72 (8.62)	53.1 (8.60)	4.04 (9.25)

T_{rip}: Temperature at resin impregnation process
The number in parentheses indicates coefficient of variation (%)

Fig. 6 Tensile strength versus fiber content

Above this level of fiber content, tensile strength starts to decrease.

As can be seen in Fig. 7, there is a continual increase in Young's modulus as fiber content increases. 50 wt% specimens increased 2.17 times higher than PP specimen.

The results for fracture strain are shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen that fracture strain is almost linearly decreased in the range of 10-50 wt%.

4 Discussion

4.1 Fiber length distribution

Injection mouldied composite specimens were dissolved in boiling xylene for 24 hours to remove PP resin. Then, extracted ramie fibers were dried at 100°C for 2 hours. Fig. 9 shows scanning electron microscopy of ramie fibers separated from composites. It can be observed that fiber surfaces do not have any separation between cells even after extrusion and injection moulding processes were applied, because lignin and pectin still exist on individual ramie fibers.

Fiber length distribution is shown in Fig. 10. Total number of counted fibers was 780, average fiber length was 1.56 mm and standard deviation was

Fig. 7 Young's modulus versus fiber content

Fig. 8 Fracture strain verses fiber content

0.61. It is necessary for short fiber reinforced composites to be longer than critical length. According to reference [8], critical length for ramie fiber is 0.47 mm. It can be clearly seen that over 98% of ramie fibers are longer than critical length in this study. This brings enough high stress to composite specimens due to matrix transfer mechanism not to cause low fiber stress.

5 Conclusions

In this study, ramie single yarns, polypropylene and maleric anhydride modified polypropylene were processed into composites using a single screw extruder and injection moulding machine. In addition to this, a new combine technique, coating and resin impregnation process, was introduced to produce continuous strands. Tensile tests were conducted by use of the strands produced at different temperatures, over a range of fiber content. We have found that the maximum mechanical properties of composites can be obtained at 195°C during resin impregnation process. We also found that Young's modulus shows continual increase over the whole range of fiber content. On the other hand, tensile strength shows a

Fig. 9 Extracted ramie fibers from composite specimens

Fig. 10 Fiber length distribution of composite specimens

maximum value at 40 wt%. Tensile strength and Young's modulus for 40 wt% composite specimens increased 1.73 times and 2.17 times, respectively, compared with PP specimens. Above 40 wt% of composites tensile strength decreased. Fracture strain linearly decreased with increasing fiber content.

A new combined technique introduced in this study is well verified that there are significant improvements of mechanical properties on composites in comparison with conventional method, in which fibers are directly inserted into extrusion process. One of the most fascinating points is the simplification to produce long natural fiber reinforced composites.

The composite strands obtained here are expected as a semi-material for injection and/or compression moulding products.

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